

IMPROVING STUDENTS' SPEAKING ABILITY THROUGH SIMULATION OF JOB INTERVIEW

¹Andi Asrifan

²Like Raskova Octaberlina

³Selviana Agus

^{1,3}Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang

²Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim, Malang, Indonesia

ABSTRACT

The aims of this study were to find out: (1) whether the use or not of Job Interview Simulation improves the speak ability of the students, and (2) whether the students are highly interested in using Job Interview Simulation for improved speech ability. The pre-experimental method used in this research was that of single-language class. In the academic year 2015-2016, the research population was the eighth grade. There were 135 students in 6 categories, each with 22-23 students, (VIII.1, VIII.2, VIII.3, VIII.4, VIII.5 and VIII.6). The researcher chose VIII.2 as representative and the total number of students is 22. The researchers have taken cluster random spectrum. The research data were collected using two types of instruments, namely test and questionnaire. The speaking examination was used to obtain data on the ability of the students to speak and the survey was used to understand the interest of students in the English language through the Job Interview Simulation. The results of the analyzes showed that after students were taught simulation work interview, there was a significant difference between their scores and before they were taught simulation work interview. The average post-test score was more than the average pre-test score (73.04>50.13). In addition, the p-value result was lower than α (0.000<0.05), meaning H1 was accepted. Then the Likert Scale analyzes of interest indicated that students would like to speak English by using the Job Interview Simulation. It has been demonstrated by 59.1% of interested students and 40.9% of interested students. Building on the data analysis, the research found: (1) the use of Job Interview Simulation improves the speaking skills of pupils; (2) it makes students interested in speaking English through the use of Job Interview Simulation.

Keyword : Simulation of Job Interview, Speaking, and Interest

INTRODUCTION

Speaking is one way of communicating which ideas by word of mouth. We need to use the language in real communication to allow students to communicate. In

Efrizal (2012), Burn and Joyce say that one of the goals for most language programs was the development of language skills, and most programs were intended to integrate both language spoken and written. To learn a language means to use it in oral or written communication and to express feelings, thoughts and experiences in different contexts.

Rebecca in Efrizal (2012) stated that speaking in the first mode of language learning is part of the everyday participation of most people and is the primary motor of change. It also provides our key information for bilingualism and linguistic communication. In Lamba (2014) O'Malley and Pierce say speech is an important skill to acquire from a learner. It is extremely important to allow students to communicate in oral languages effectively, because students' incapacity to speak could not allow them to express their ideas in a simple way.

Based on research experience and the finding that the student is often reluctant to speak because they fear correct words or because students feel shy about talking to another student, although everyone knows that the best way to speak a language is to learn to speak the language.

If students don't learn how to speak in the language school, then they may soon become boring and lose interest in foreign language learning. However, if the proper activities are taught correctly, it may be a lot of fun to speak in the classroom, increase the general motivation and make English an enjoyable and dynamic place.

The researcher is interested in analyzing some problems in the day-to-day conversations and learning processes that make student speak English seldom. Because in this case, students must be more active than teacher in trying to use one way to enhance the abilities of the students. It can be tested by Job Interview simulation. Using the work interview simulation, students can motivate themselves to talk, because with their words and imagination, they can answer the questions.

In this research the researcher will lead the title "Improvement of students who speak capacity by simulating work interviews at SMP Negeri 2 Panca Rijang's Eighth-Grade Students."

METHODS

Population and Sample

The population of this research was the eighth grade students in academic year 2015-2016. There were 135 students spread in 6 classes (VIII.1, VIII.2, VIII.3, VIII.4, VIII.5 and VIII.6) and each class consist appropriately 22-23 students. The researcher took cluster random sampling technique and chose VIII.2 as the representative and the number of total sample is 22 students.

Instrument of the Research

The data of the research were collected by using two kinds of instruments, namely speaking test and questionnaire. Speaking test (interview) was used to obtain data of the students' speaking ability and questionnaire was used to know the students interest in speaking English by using Simulation of Job Interview.

Procedure of Collecting Data

Procedure of collecting data was divided into two stages, namely pre-test and post-test.

1. Pre-test

Before giving treatment, the research gave speaking test to students in interview one by one.

2. Post-test

After giving the treatment, the students were given a set of speaking test and questionnaire.

Treatment

The researcher would conduct treatment for students by using Simulation of Job Interview. It would be done for four meetings. The researcher gave Simulation of Job Interview to the students based on theme. There are four topics namely Office Supervisor, Administrator, Travel Agent, and Doctor.

The researcher teaches about Simulation of Job Interview every meeting or each material with time allocation is 80 minutes (2 X 40 minutes). The steps in teaching speaking by using technique were:

1. The researcher gave greeting for the students.
2. The researcher checks list the name of students in class.
3. The researcher gave a motivation to each student before teaching the material.
4. The researcher introduced Simulation of Job Interview to help the students in their learning process, .
5. The researcher gave example about the material orally.
6. The researcher gave chance to each student to ask for unclearly material.
7. The researcher instructs the students to speak English.
8. The researcher explained and corrected the students' probable mistake in speaking.

RESULT

Findings

This section deals with the presentation of students' achievement in speaking consist into three parts fluency, accuracy, and comprehensibility.

a. Scoring Classification of Students' Test.

Before and after giving a test, the researcher analyzed the students' score of one class (pre-test and post-test). The scoring classification of the students score is presented in table 1.

Table 1 The Classification of Scoring Students Pre-Test and Post-Test

NO	Classification	Score	Pre-test		Post-test	
			F	%	F	%
1	Excellent	87 – 100	0	0	5	22.7
2	Very good	73 – 86	0	0	5	22.7
3	Good	59 – 72	6	27.3	10	45.6
4	Average	45 – 58	6	27.3	2	9.0
5	Poor	30 – 44	8	36.4	0	0
6	Very poor	< 30	2	9.0	0	0
Total			22	100.0	22	100.0

Table 1 shows that the students' score in test result for monolingual class (pre-test) most of them are in very poor category, 2 (9.0%) students are classified into poor, 8 (36.4%) students are classified into average and good, 6 (27.3%). There are not any students classified into excellent and very good category. While test result for monolingual class (post-test) most of them are in average category, 2 (9.0%) student are classified into good, 10 (45.6%) student are classified into very good and excellent, 5 (22.7%) There are not any students classified into poor and very poor category. It means that the students ability in speaking had ben improve because most of the students score is increase. It shows that the students speaking ability is higher after learning English by using Simulation of Job Interview.

b. The Mean Score and Standar Deviation of the Students' Test Result

In this part, the discussion deals with the argument of the difference of the students' speaking skill before and after giving test. The mean score of test class VIII.2 in pre-test and post-test is significantly different. The findings of test are presented in the following table.

Table 2 The Mean Score and Standard Deviation of the Students' Test

Class VIII.2	Mean Score	Standard Deviation
PRE-TEST	50.13	13.809
POST-TEST	73.04	11.878

Based on the table above show that the mean score of class VIII.2 pre-test and post-test is different. The mean score of post-test (73.04) was higher than the mean score of pre-test (50.13). The standard deviation of pre-test is 13.809 and

standard deviation of post-test is 11.878. It means there is a significant different between students' pre-test and post-test.

c. The Students Interest

The results show the students have been interested in speaking English by using Simulation of Job Interview. These results can be seen on table 3:

Table 3 The Percentage of Students' Interest

Category	Range	Frequency	%
Strongly Interested	85-100	13	59.1
Interested	69-84	9	40.9
Moderate	52-68	0	0
Uninterested	36-51	0	0
Strongly Uninterested	20-35	0	0
Total		22	100.0

Based on the percentage analysis of students' interest on the table 3 above, the analysis showed that there were no students who states negative statement to the use of Simulation of Job Interview in improving students' speaking ability, 13 students (59.1%) were strongly interested who got score in interval 85-100 and 9 students (40.9%) were interested in interval 69-84. The table above indicates the use of Simulation of Job Interview in improving students' speaking ability is strongly interesting to the students. This is supported by the following table:

Table 4 Mean Score of Students' Interest

Total respondent	Total of students' score	Mean
22	1890	85.90

The table 4 shows that the mean score of students' interest is 85.90. It means the students strongly interested to use Simulation of Job Interview in speaking English.

d. Probability Value (P-Value)

The hypothesis stated was tested by using inferential analysis. In this case, the researcher applied paired samples t-test analysis using SPSS 21.0 program for Windows Evaluation Version. The result of calculating was shown as follow:

Table 5 The P-Value of Students Speaking

α	P-Value
0,05	0,000

In pre-test and post-test, the researcher found that the p-value was lower than the α ($0,000 < 0,05$). This means that H_0 was rejected and H_1 accepted. It means that teaching speaking through Simulation of Job Interview has the good effect to the students speaking ability.

Discussion

On the basis of the above results, it was demonstrated to improve SMP Negeri 2 Panca Rijang's speaking abilities in the application of Job Interview Simulation.

As described in the previous section, the summary of the data gathered during the test showed that students' speakability improves greatly. The average score of the student test in class VIII is supported² (post-test). The average after-test score of 73.04 is 50.13 higher than the previous test score. The results from the last section showed that using Job Interview Simulation in teaching language is more efficient than using Job Interview Simulation. The difference between the average value of pre- and post-test is sponsored.

These data show that the use of work interview simulation increases the speaking skills of students substantially. Using Job Interview Simulation in the speech process gives students a better effect than using conventional technologies. This result follows what Umarok (2015) has claimed in his research that the use of simulation technology has successfully improved the ability of the students to communicate. It can motivate and encourage students to speak English actively. Sudirman et al. (2012) stated in the research that the interview technique is effective in encouraging students to actively and fluently speak English in the course. This result answered the question of research that use of job interview simulation improve the ability of students to speak and increase the interest of students in speaking. It has been demonstrated by the interest of 59.1% of students and 40.9% of students.

The researcher uses p-value inferential statistic by SPSS version 21.0 to test the hypothesis, based on the results of students obtained and stated in the above findings. In other words, after applying Simulation of the Job Interview at SMP Negeri 2, Panca Rijang class VIII.2 there is an improvement on students' speaking ability.

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